

A Bibliography of Racial Hereditarian Research

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Since 2012, over 350 journal articles and books claim, either in whole or in part, that folk racial classifications are biologically meaningful categories and that racial differences in intelligence test scores, educational attainment, income, and crime partly or even primarily originate from genetic differences between those races. Some psychologists claim that the differences between White Europeans and Black Africans or African Americans are highly resistant to change, and result from evolved differences in brain size, testosterone, and reproductive strategies produced by natural selection. We refer to this body of work as “racial hereditarian research” or RHR and the authors as “RHR psychologists.”

This bibliography lists these works which argue for all, or part, of RHR since 2012. Work which use “national differences,” skin reflectance, continent, or latitude as proxies for race are included. We chose 2012 as that starting date because that was the year that two of the most prolific RHR psychologists, Arthur Jensen and Philippe Rushton, died. The few references that pre-date 2012 are quoted in our paper and included here for convenience.

We have included, at a minimum:

- Articles in the "Tribute to Richard Lynn" issue of *Personality and Individual Differences*, 53(2), 2012.
- Articles in the “Tribute to Philippe Rushton” issue of *Personality and Individual Differences*, 55(3), 2013.
- Articles in MDPI *Psych* Special Issue "Beyond Thirty Years of Research on Race Differences in Cognitive Ability" 1(1), 2019.
- Works citing or using Lynn’s National IQ Dataset or Lynn’s “Cold Weather Theory” or related flawed evolutionary theories.
- Articles featuring the idea of a “taboo” on RHR and the ethical and scientific reasonableness of RHR

Articles by León contain some arguments that are superficially anti-hereditarian. We explain the reasons for the inclusion of León’s articles in Bird, Jackson, and Winston, (2025; <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0001528>). We have annotated these entries with an asterisk.

There are three sections to the bibliography:

1. Journal Articles. We note instances where these articles are abstracted on White nationalist websites.
2. Books, including those published by mainstream publishers (eg. Cambridge University Press) and White nationalist publishers (e.g. Washington Summit Publishers).
3. RHR psychologists’ writings and interviews appearing on White Nationalist websites.

We do not claim this list is exhaustive. RHR psychologists often claim that their work is taboo or somehow banned from publication. RHR psychologists also claim their research is value-neutral and apolitical. This bibliography should show that these claims are false. Works engaging with RHR are listed in **Bibliography of Critical Responses to Racial Hereditarian Research**; far from taboo, RHR and race generally, is vigorously debated in the scientific literature.

Section 1: Articles.

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Section 2: Books

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Section 3: RHR on White Nationalist Websites.

Note:

- Because readers of *American Psychologist* are probably unfamiliar with these websites, they may consult the following references for proper context:
 - American Renaissance: <https://www.splcenter.org/fighting-hate/extremist-files/group/american-renaissance>
 - Arktos Media: (<https://www.theatlantic.com/international/archive/2017/05/how-hungary-became-a-haven-for-the-alt-right/527178/>)
 - Occidental Quarterly: <https://www.splcenter.org/fighting-hate/extremist-files/group/occidental-quarterly>
 - Radix Journal: <https://www.theatlantic.com/politics/archive/2018/09/a-daily-caller-editor-wrote-for-an-alt-right-website-using-a-pseudonym/569335/>
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 - Stephan Molyneux: <https://www.splcenter.org/20180419/mcinnis-molyneux-and-4chan-investigating-pathways-alt-right>
 - Unz Review: <https://www.adl.org/resources/blog/california-entrepreneur-ron-unz-launches-series-rhetorical-attacks-jews>
 - VDARE: <https://www.splcenter.org/fighting-hate/extremist-files/group/vdare>
- Many of these posts are cross-posted on other White Nationalist websites; nearly everything at VDARE.com is cross-posted to Unz.com, for example. We list only the original posting.
- We do not document the regular column by psychologist James Thompson at the Unz Review. Since 2012 he has written over 1000 columns for Unz (<https://www.unz.com/author/james-thompson/>)

- We have not documented the dozens of articles psychologist Kevin MacDonald has written for *The Occidental Quarterly*, the journal he edits. He has an article in nearly every issue.
- We have not tried to document the countless references to RHR in these websites, only the direct participation of RHR psychologists. .

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[Topic: "Human Biodiversity." Speakers: Edward Dutton, Kevin MacDonald, Helmuth Nyborg, Greg Johnson (author of *White Nationalist Manifesto*), Fróði Midjord.]